

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 727247 (SolACE)

SolACE - Solutions for improving Agroecosystem and Crop Efficiency for water and nutrient use

Deliverable D4.2 New GS models for bread and durum wheat

Planned delivery date (as in DoA): Month M24, April 2019

Actual submission date: 31/05/2018 (Month M25) – Revised 07/09/2020

Work package: WP4

Work package leader: Nicola Pecchioni, CREA

Deliverable leader: Renaud Rincent / Jacques Le Gouis (INRAE, Clermont Ferrand)

Author: Renaud Rincent, INRAE, Giovanni Laidò, CREA, Nicola Pecchioni, CREA, and Jacques Le Gouis, INRAE

Version: 2.0

This Deliverable is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 727247.	
Dissemination Level	
PU Public	X
CI Classified, as referred to Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
CO Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Research and Innovation action: GA no. 727247

Start date of the project: May 1st, 2017

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	3
2. Results.....	3
3. Conclusions	5
4. Partners involved in the work.....	5
5. Annexes.....	5

1. Introduction

The development of the root system is a key feature for plants to face abiotic stress. The characteristics of the root system can indeed make more nutrient or water available to the plant at key growth stages. It was for example shown that varieties with deeper root system could be more productive in drought conditions (Manschadi et al. 2006 ; Ehdaie et al. 2012). However, these traits have rarely been selected directly by plant breeders, because of the difficulty to phenotype below-ground traits and because of their interaction with the environment. High-throughput phenotyping platforms such as those developed by INRAE and UCL can be used to intensively characterize root traits for panels of diversity at early stages of growth. This was done successfully within SolACE for bread and durum wheat. It revealed large genetic variabilities for all traits in both bread and durum wheat. The phenotypic data collected within SolACE could thus be combined with genotypic data available from previous projects to apply association mapping and genomic selection strategies.

One example of the existence of major QTL can be found in literature for rice (Uga et al. 2013), but most studies suggest that these traits are highly polygenic (many genes are involved). So we decided to focus on a genomic selection (GS) strategy, which seems more appropriate for this kind of trait, because in GS the selection is based on all markers taken together. This allows capturing a more important part of the genetic variability than when doing classical marker assisted selection based on few QTLs only. GS has also the advantage of being fast, as selection can be made without phenotypic evaluation once the prediction model is calibrated. GS will be carried out within SolACE to produce homozygous lines with improved root traits. The project aims at obtaining improved lines within the timeframe of the project. The GS prediction and selection are to be coupled to a doubled haploid (DH) production strategy, in order to obtain rapidly homozygous lines ready to be tested for validation of the selection strategy. To keep the pace with the future planned activities, generation F1 seeds of both bread and durum wheat had to be ready for summer 2019, in order to produce DH lines. In the present deliverable, we present how the genotypic and root phenotypic data were combined to calibrate a GS model and evaluate its accuracy using cross-validation.

Ehdaie B, Layne AP, Waines JG (2012) Root system plasticity to drought influences grain yield in bread wheat. *Euphytica* 186:219–232.

Manschadi AM, Christopher J, Devoil P, Hammer GL (2006) The role of root architectural traits in adaptation of wheat to water-limited environments. *Functional Plant Biology* 33, 823–837.

Uga Y, Sugimoto K, Ogawa S, et al (2013) Control of root system architecture by DEEPER ROOTING 1 increases rice yield under drought conditions. *Nat Genet* 45:1097–1102.

2. Results

The root phenotypic data collected within the SolACE project and the genotypic data obtained in other projects (notably PIA BreedWheat) were combined to calibrate reference genomic prediction models. A model was calibrated for each of the key traits measured in the high-throughput phenotyping platforms (INRAE Dijon, and UCL Louvain), including root angle, root length, root and shoot biomass and root/shoot ratio at harvest. The same reference RRBLUP model was applied to both species, as it is particularly well adapted to highly polygenic traits. RRBLUP is a reference GS model in which it is assumed that all markers have an effect sampled from a same distribution. It is particularly adapted to highly polygenic traits such as root traits, and is equivalent to the GBLUP model, another reference GS model in which a kinship matrix is

estimated with all markers and used as variance/covariance matrix in a mixed model. These models usually perform at least as good as more sophisticated Bayesian model in the absence of major QTL (Heslot et al. 2012).

One common way to validate a prediction model in the absence of independent dataset is to evaluate the predictive ability using cross-validations. For each trait, predictive abilities were evaluated with 5-fold cross-validation schemes with 10 replicates (see Annexes section for the R script). For each replicate, we randomly splitted the dataset into five folds, and used in turn the phenotypes of four of the five folds to predict the remaining fold. Predictive ability was estimated for each fold as the correlation between the predictions and the adjusted means of the validation set (predicted fold).

Table 1: Predictive ability of the RRBLUP GS model for each trait for bread and durum wheat.

Trait	Predictive ability (bread wheat)	Predictive ability (durum wheat)
Root Biomass	0.29*	0.24*
Shoot Biomass	0.25*	0.20*
Seminal root angle	0.13*	0.15
Number of seminal roots	0.42*	0.37
Root depth	0.27*	0.42**
Root/shoot ratio	0.34*	0.30*

* datasets from INRAE Dijon's phenotyping platform

** 0.42 for seminal root depth, 0.34 for primary root length

Predictive abilities were low to intermediate (Table 1), ranging from 0.13 to 0.42. It was particularly low for root angle for both bread and durum wheat. In bread wheat, predictive abilities were higher for root and shoot biomass at harvest and for the ratio of root to shoot biomass at harvest. It is important to note that we expect this trait to be related to water stress tolerance in the field. However, for durum wheat, due to the delay in delivering the root/shoot ratio data from the INRAE Dijon's phenotyping platform (*), this trait was not used to select for complementary parents in the crossing season of April 2019. Other traits have been used as planned, i.e. root depth and seminal root angle, thus allowing the prosecution of WP4 Task 4.2 activities.

Datasets collected within other projects on the same material will be used to improve the heritabilities of the adjusted means, and thus the predictive abilities of the GS models.

Heslot N, Yang H-P, Sorrells ME, Jannink J-L (2012) Genomic selection in plant breeding: A comparison of models. *Crop Sci.* 52:146–160.

3. Conclusions

A reference GS model (RRBLUP) was successfully calibrated for bread and durum wheat for below-ground traits (see the R script in Annexes). The predictive abilities appeared to be low to intermediate in 5-folds cross-validation schemes. We conclude that the GS models are validated, and expect predictive abilities to

increase by using complementary phenotypic datasets obtained on the same high-throughput phenotyping platforms. At this step, the GS models were only used to identify complementary parents to generate DH lines. GS models will be applied in a next step to identify the most promising DH lines for the considered traits.

4. Partners involved in the work

INRAE, CREA

5. Annexes

R script for the calibration and evaluation of RRBLUP GS model on below-ground traits using cross-validation

```
install.packages("rrBLUP") # install GS package for RRBLUP (or equivalently GBLUP)
library(rrBLUP)

Nrep=10      # Nb of replicates of the 5 folds cross-validation

Nind=nrow(matGY) # Nind is the number of individuals (varieties), matGY is the matrix of adjusted means
Ntrait=ncol(matGY) # Ntrait is the number of traits to be tested

corsaveGBLUP=matrix(NA,(5*Nrep),Ntrait) # Initialize the matrix of predictive abilities

for (trait in 1:Ntrait) { # Loop on the traits to be predicted
  print(trait)

  cpt=0
  for (rep in 1:Nrep) { # Loop on the replicates

    folds=rep(seq(1,5),round(Nind/5)+1) # folds is the random sampling of the 5 folds
    folds=sample(folds[1:Nind],165)

    for (fd in 1:5) { # Loop on the folds
      cpt=cpt+1
      cal=which(folds!=fd) # Define the calibration set
      val= which(folds==fd) # Define the validation set

      Zd=matrix(0,length(cal),ncol(matA1)) # matA1 is the kinship matrix, Zd is the design matrix
      for (cl in 1:length(cal)) { Zd[cl,cal[cl]]=1}

      rrBLUP=mixed.solve(y=matGY[cal,trait], Z=Zd, K=matA1, method="REML",bounds=c(1e-09,
      1e+09), SE=FALSE, return.Hinv=FALSE) # Calibrate the RRBLUP model on the calibration set

      predict=rrBLUP$u # Get predictions (BLUPs) of the validation set

      corsaveGBLUP[cpt,trait]=cor(predict[val],matGY[val,trait],use="complete.obs") # compute
      # and save predictive ability
    } # End of loop on folds
  } # End of loop on replicates
} # End of loop on traits

MeanAbility=apply(corsaveGBLUP,2,mean) # Compute the average predictive ability for each trait
```